

Engineering and
Physical Sciences
Research Council

Second-order computational homogenisation: A multi-scale modelling framework for shell elements

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EXETER

Multi-scale framework for large structures

- Large components are modelled as shells, i.e. wing panels, turbine blades and fuselage.
- Computationally efficient, but:
 - Cannot account for sub-structural defects, ie wrinkles/ply drops, nor their effects on the stiffness/strength response
 - Limited capability for progressive damage modelling – cannot account for delamination

the idea: Link the shell elements with a multi-scale framework
using *second-order homogenisation*

Comparison between 1st and 2nd order homogenisation

First order homogenisation – linking solid to solid

RVE deformation modes

Comparison between 1st and 2nd order homogenisation

Second order homogenisation – linking shell to solid

Framework formulation

Macro-scale: 5-parameter shell (first-order shear)

Downscaling:

In-plane periodic b.c.

- + Surface fluctuation moment (bending)
- + Volumetric fluctuation moment (t.shear)

Upscaling:

- RVE stress averaging
- Static condensation of RVE stiffness matrix
- Yields force/moment resultants, ABD and transverse shear stiffness matrices

Transverse shear deformation

With volume constraint

Without volume constraint

RVE deformation modes

Concurrent FE2 framework

- In Abaqus/Standard
- An RVE analysis for each integration point, at every iteration

Example (1): Reconstruction of nonlinear stresses

Example (2): Elastic post-buckling analysis

Example (3): Transverse shear correction factor for sandwich panel

Comparison with analytical solution

Panels with different facesheet-to-core stiffness ratios

- Reference, $\alpha_{cf} = 1/10$
- Multi-scale, $\alpha_{cf} = 1/10$
- Reference, $\alpha_{cf} = 1/25$
- Multi-scale, $\alpha_{cf} = 1/25$
- Reference, $\alpha_{cf} = 1/50$
- ▲ Multi-scale, $\alpha_{cf} = 1/50$
- Reference, $\alpha_{cf} = 1/500$
- ▼ Multi-scale, $\alpha_{cf} = 1/500$

Example (4): Plate delamination under shear load

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Test case 1: Delamination under shear load

Example (5): Delamination during post-buckling

Material: CFRP

Layup: (0/90/0/90/0/90)

Example (5): Delamination during post-buckling

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Other layups and material

— Direct numerical simulation
 ● Multi-scale shell model

Summary and outlook

- Multi-scale framework for shell elements based on 2nd order computational homogenisation
- Currently:
 - Scaling up the approach for woven RVE models – the additional constraint equations are dense, and Abaqus cannot handle them without running into memory issues.